

A QUAD 1x16 CMOS ROIC WITH FULLY DIFFERENTIAL CTIA-CDS FOR ORTHOGONALLY MODULATED 2-D ACTIVE IMAGING SYSTEMS

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INTRODUCTION

Design of readout circuits for infrared imaging systems is increasingly challenging due to larger format photodetector arrays with smaller pixels, coupled with requirements for higher sensitivity and lower power dissipation. Traditional readout techniques involve photocurrent-to-voltage conversion at the cell level by means of an integrating capacitor [1]. Our previous work [2] demonstrates an alternative readout scheme that uses orthogonal carriers to modulate the photo currents so that the signals from an entire row can be read simultaneously without loss of optical power. In order to improve the system sensitivity and to minimize the effects of electronic offset and power supply noise, a fully differential architecture has been implemented. Thus, at the end of each row, the differential row busses are fed to fully differential capacitive transimpedance amplifiers (CTIA's) that take care of the current-to-voltage conversion. Their outputs are driven externally for digitization and post processing. Figure 1 shows a block diagram representation of the system. The remaining of this paper describes the design, fabrication and prototype testing of the fully differential CTIA amplifier shown in Figure 2.

Figure 1 ROIC architecture

Figure 2 Differential CTIA with correlated double sampling

FULLY DIFFERENTIAL CTIA WITH CORRELATED DOUBLE SAMPLING (CDS)

The capacitive transimpedance amplifier was designed according to the sensitivity and charge integration requirements of the system. The major components are the fully differential operational transconductance amplifier OTA and the set of CMOS switches and matched capacitors that compose the charge integration module and the correlated double sampling structure (see Figure 2). The fully differential structure is preferred over the pseudo-differential one because of its advantages in terms of lower pedestal errors and residual charge injection cancellation. Those two phenomena become common-mode signals in the fully differential architecture and are consequently mitigated by a subsequent differential amplifier (not shown). Special care was taken in the physical design of C_{CDS} , sample and hold C_{SH} , and integration C_{int} capacitors from Figure 2, as well as in the CMOS switches to guarantee low mismatches that minimize differences between the true and complementary signals V_{op} , V_{on} .

In order to satisfy the sensitivity and dynamic settling requirements of the CTIA structure, we designed a fully differential OTA with an open loop gain higher than 40,000 V/V and total transconductance greater than 250 mS/e. The chosen topology for its implementation was a two-stage, Miller-compensated operational amplifier. Because of its fully differential nature, the circuit also required a common-mode-feedback amplifier to stabilize its common-mode output voltage to the desired near-zero volts. Special care was taken to guarantee the overall amplifier was stable under the two different loading scenarios: first, the charge integration interval, during which the amplifier operates with the feedback integration capacitor and second, the reset interval, in which the amplifier is in unitary feedback configuration. To ensure stability, an additional compensation capacitor was switched in during the reset interval, thus providing enough phase margin to the system.

QUAD 1x16 ORTHOGONALLY ENCODED ROIC WITH DIFFERENTIAL CTIA-CDS ARCHITECTURE

We have fabricated a CMOS test chip containing four arrays of 16 readout cells to verify the circuit designs and to demonstrate the operation of the fully differential architecture for the orthogonal readout cell encoding from previous work [2]. The readout integrated circuit (ROIC) test chip was fabricated in a 0.5- μm , 5V process that has feature sizes appropriate for full-scale chips. The fabrication technology includes 2 poly layers and 3 layers of metal.

The integrated circuit was implemented using dual power supplies of $\pm 2.5V$ and it is intended to operate in conjunction with 1MHz orthogonal codes. The two layers of poly silicon were used to build C_{CDS} , C_{SH} and C_{int} . Complementary MOS transistors were used to design the switches. Figure 3 shows a photograph of the test chip. The CMOS die was glued and wire-bonded to a custom printed circuit board (pcb). This chip-on-board layout allows the readout chip to interface with laboratory signal sources or with MSM photo detector elements. Figure 4 shows the test board configured for electrical testing. The code modulation signals, control signals for the CTIA-CDS operation, and the electrical test input signals are connected at the bottom edges of the board.

Figure 3 Quad 1x16 test chip with differential CTIA-CDS

Figure 4 Chip-On-Board test system

For prototype verification we constructed the system shown in Figure 5. The experiment was designed to demonstrate the fully differential current to voltage conversion of a single input current, and to show its advantages over the pseudo-differential configuration. The modulating codes and control signals for the CTIA-CDS circuitry are synthesized with the pattern generator and amplitude/bias conditioned before connecting them to the board.

Figure 5 Test system setup for the CTIA-CDS verification

Figure 6 True/complementary and differential outputs

TEST RESULTS

We used a laboratory voltage signal generator followed by a large (10 MOhm) on-board series resistor to emulate a current source detector element. The source was set to produce 200mV that with the series resistor creates a 20 nA input dc current. The current flows directly into the CTIA-CDS structure and gets integrated in the feedback capacitor. Every $1\mu s$, the control signals guarantee that the voltage across the integration capacitor is reset to zero. The output voltages must be sampled and digitized at the end of each integration cycle, before the next reset signal arrives. Figure 6 shows the true and complementary signals at the output of the differential CTIA, as well as the differential voltage resulting from their subtraction.

CONCLUSION

We obtained satisfactory results for the proof-of-principle experiment presented in this paper. We think the fully differential CTIA-CDS architecture demonstrated here is the best candidate for the encoding readout technique presented in previous work [2]. Thanks to the fully differential nature of the CTIA-CDS, the system sensitivity and noise rejection capability is considerably improved. For comparison purposes with the single-ended version of the system, refer to the true or complementary signals in Figure 6. Note that the charge injection and pedestal levels are considerably lower in the fully differential signaling scheme.

REFERENCES

- [1] C.-C. Hsieh, C.-Y. Wu, F.-W. Jih, and T.-P. Sun, "Focal plane arrays and CMOS readout techniques of infrared imaging systems," *IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems for Video Technology*, vol. 7, 1997.
- [2] J. Garcia, W. Lawler, N. Waite and F. Kiamilev, "0.5um CMOS orthogonal encoding readout cell for active imaging systems", *IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Quantum Electronics*, pp. 803-810, vol. 10, num. 4, July-August 2004.